

SOME OBSERVATIONS ON MECHANICAL AND FRACTURE PROPERTIES OF AN $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{SiC}_w$ CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

The objective of the work reported here was to examine the effectiveness of an inert atmosphere on the mechanical properties and crack growth behaviour of alumina reinforced with silicon carbide whiskers at 1200°C. The mechanical properties, fracture toughness and crack growth rates were determined over a range of strain rates. It was found that the creep deformation and extensive crack formation that limits the performance of SiC whisker reinforced alumina at temperatures around 1200°C in air are also operative in a practical inert atmosphere.

Keywords: alumina, composites, high-temperature, strength, toughness.

1. INTRODUCTION

The major advantage of a ceramic matrix composite (CMC) over a monolithic ceramic is that the former can provide substantial improvement in toughness over the latter through a number of mechanisms such as crack deflection, crack bridging, debonding and pull-out [1,2]. For this reason CMCs are considered potentially much better materials than monolithic ceramics, particularly at high temperatures. At Ansto we have a materials requirement for a component that will operate in an argon atmosphere and be subjected to thermal shock and repeated compressive loads at 1200°C, while being compatible with other materials in the operation. These conditions are just beyond the limits of present engineering materials. A broad research program is currently being undertaken to study the high temperature properties of a series of CMCs. In the present paper, some preliminary results are presented for a composite material containing 30 vol% SiC whiskers in an alumina matrix.

Previous work [3] has shown that the addition of SiC whiskers renders alumina based composites susceptible to oxidation effects. Surfaces exposed to air at 800°C showed a reaction at the SiC interface, at 1000° and 1200°C discontinuous glass films formed, while at 1400°C a continuous layer of glass, pores and mullite crystals was produced. The parabolic rates of scale formation in air at temperatures in the range 1310°-1525°C have been measured for alumina with SiC whiskers and particles [4]. It has been proposed that sufficient SiC should be present to convert all the alumina in the oxidation scale to mullite, or a rigid non-protective scale will be formed. Even so, the thermal expansion mismatch between mullite or mullite plus silica may be too great for good protection under thermal cycling conditions [4].

When tested in air, creep and associated crack nucleation and growth is observed at temperatures of 1200°C and above [3]. The effects are attributed to low viscosity of the glassy phase at 1200°C leading to grain boundary penetration and promotion of creep and crack formation. The apparent fracture toughness is increased, but the strength, retained strength, stress-rupture properties and creep properties are significantly degraded.

The creep rate in nitrogen is significantly lower than in air [5]. At 1200°C and at low stresses at higher temperatures the mechanism was grain boundary diffusion with some unaccommodated grain boundary sliding, while at higher temperatures and stresses the unaccommodated grain boundary sliding dominated with increased grain boundary cavitation.

Crack growth at 1100° to 1300°C in argon has been compared with monolithic aluminas [6]. The crack nucleation was enhanced by the whiskers, attributed to an interlocking of small grains to form whisker/matrix agglomerates which effectively act as grains. Cracks tend to nucleate at local heterogeneities in whisker orientation.

The aim of the work reported here was to further examine the effectiveness of inert atmosphere, particularly with respect to the mechanical properties and crack growth behaviour at 1200°C.

Figure 1

A schematic diagram showing the dimensions of the specimens relative to the original hot-pressed billet, also an indication of the alignment of the whiskers and the bend jig dimensions.

All dimensions are in millimeters

2. MATERIALS AND METHOD

The $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{SiC}_w$ composite was obtained from commercial sources [7] as a disc cut from a hot-pressed billet (dimensions 100 mm diameter). Microstructural examination indicated that the preferred orientation of the whiskers was perpendicular to the compression direction in the hot-pressed billet (that is plane C in Figure 1). The whisker diameters ranged from 0.2-0.8 μm and their lengths were 3-35 μm . The composition of the material was confirmed as Al_2O_3 and SiC by X-ray diffraction. Four point bend specimens with dimensions 4.0 x 3.0 x 43 mm (Figure 1) were cut with a diamond saw and the surface polished to 4-8 μm diamond paste finish. For fracture toughness and crack growth rates, three small (150 μm) cracks were placed 5 mm apart on the tension face using a Vickers diamond pyramid indenter with a 5 kg load, whereas for conventional mechanical properties, no indentations were made on the specimens. In general, two tests were carried out at each condition.

The bending tests were carried out on an Instron 8561 instrument at 1200°C at 1, 5 and 500 $\mu\text{m}/\text{min}$. displacement rate in an atmosphere of flowing argon (15 litre/min., commercial high-purity grade). A limited number of tests were also carried out at ambient temperature in air for comparison purposes.

Fracture toughness K_{IC} , at ambient temperature, was determined from 4-point bend specimens containing three 5 kg indentations using the following equations [8]:

$$K_{IC} = \eta (E/H)^{1/8} (\sigma_F p)^{1/3} c^{3/4} \quad (1)$$

where η is a material independent constant equal to 0.65, E is the Young's modulus [9], H is the hardness, σ_F is the fracture stress [10] and p is the indenter load.

In addition, K_{IC} at ambient temperature was also determined using Vickers and Knoop hardness indentation tests (500 g load, six indentations) on the three cross-section planes A, B and C using the following equations [11] to compare with the K_{IC} values calculated from the four point bending tests.

$$K_{IC} = 0.016 (E/H)^{1/2} p/c^{3/2} \quad (2)$$

where c is the indentation crack length and the ratio of E/H is calculated using the following equation [12]:

$$H/E = (0.14 - b/a) / 0.45 \quad (3)$$

where a and b are the long and short diagonals of the Knoop impression.

At 1200°C the fracture toughness was determined from 4-point bend specimens containing the indentations using [8]:

$$K_{IC} = (4 \psi \sigma_F \sqrt{c_m}) / 3 \quad (4)$$

where ψ is a constant about 1.44, c_m is the average length of the indentation induced crack after the test and σ_F is the fracture stress for four point bending [10]:

Table 1
Results from bend tests at 1200°C (mean of two tests).

Displacement Rate microns/minute	Modulus of Elasticity GPa	Fracture Stress MPa	Apparent K_{IC} MPa. \sqrt{m}	Crack Growth Rate microns/second
1	184	—	—	0.0025
5	223	302	22	0.25
500	248	382	9.3	1.65

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. The K_{IC} measurements at ambient temperature using indentation measurements show a dependence on orientation with respect to the hot-pressing direction, with the toughness in the plane in which the whiskers are preferentially aligned being significantly higher (planes A and B, 3.5 MPa. \sqrt{m} ; plane C, 5.0 MPa. \sqrt{m}). There was good agreement with the K_{IC} measurements from two bend tests at ambient temperature (mean 5.6 MPa. \sqrt{m}).

2. At 1200°C, the mechanical properties show strong strain rate dependence, with the modulus of elasticity, the fracture stress and apparent K_{IC} values increasing as the strain rate increases (Table 1). The material is far from linearly elastic at 1200°C (Figure 2), and the apparent K_{IC} at 1200°C is significantly higher than at ambient.

3. Although the tests at 1200°C were carried out in flowing high purity argon, some oxidation did occur and a thin (about 5 μ m) scale formed on all surfaces (Figure 3), which was removed by polishing to fully reveal the cracking. A similar observation has been reported by other workers [6], indicating a sensitivity to trace amounts of oxygen in this material.

4. Extensive cracking was observed, originating on the tensile face (Figures 3, 4).

5. The overall crack growth rates varied as the strain rate (Table 1).

6. At both 5 and 1 μ m/min. strain rate, the stress-strain curves exhibit serrations indicating a "stick-slip" behaviour (Figure 2). These features are absent at the 500 μ m/min. strain rate.

7. Only with the fast strain rate (500 μ m/min.) at 1200°C did crack propagation from the indentation result in failure. With the 5 μ m/min. strain rate, although the indentation cracks did propagate (for example from 160 to 2340 μ m), the specimens were fractured from cracks initiated on the tensile surfaces away from the indentations (Figure 4). No fracture occurred for all 1 μ m/min. strain rate specimens which bent plastically for more than 5 hours before the tests were stopped. These observations and the "stick-slip" behaviour are consistent with a crack arrest mechanism such as crack blunting [3] operating at slow strain rates.

Figure 2: Stress strain relationships: solid line - indented specimens, broken line - plain specimens

8. The fracture surfaces from the slow (5 $\mu\text{m}/\text{min}$.) strain rate tests at 1200°C showed significant whisker pull-out and rougher fracture surfaces than those from the fast (500 $\mu\text{m}/\text{min}$.) strain rate tests at 1200°C and those at ambient temperature. Three zones of the fracture surface can be identified: in the slow-crack growth region the fracture is intergranular with extensive whisker pull-out (Figure 5), an intermediate region and the final fast fracture region of predominantly transgranular fracture with limited whisker pull-out (Figure 6).

5. CONCLUSIONS

This work indicates that the creep deformation and extensive crack formation that limits the performance of SiC whisker reinforced alumina at temperatures around 1200°C in air are also operative in a practical inert atmosphere.

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Figure 3. SEM micrograph of a specimen exposed to 1200°C for four hours in flowing argon, showing the oxide layer and crack propagation from an indentation.

Figure 4. Optical micrograph of a broken specimen tested at 1200°C at 5µm/min. The oxide layer has been removed to show the extensive cracking. Mag. 32X, 312.5µm bar.

Figure 5. SEM micrograph of a slow crack growth region on the fracture surface, showing significant intergranular fracture and whisker pull-out.

Figure 6. SEM micrograph of the same specimen as Figure 5 from the fast crack growth region, showing predominantly transgranular fracture and limited whisker pull-out.

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